

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF EARLY DETERMINATION OF STUDENTS' SPORTS TALENT

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JDPU. Sport turlarini o'qitish metodikasi kafedrasida dotsenti.

Abstract: *The main reasons for the inability of primary school children to objectively assess the capabilities of their desires are the selection of gifted students and their targeted training.*

Key words: *Secondary school, skills, athletic ability, sports.*

Аннотация: *Основными причинами неспособности младших школьников младшего школьного возраста объективно оценить возможности своих желаний являются задачи отбора и отбора из их числа талантливых учеников.*

Ключевые слова: *Средняя школа, навыки, спортивные способности, спорт.*

Annotasiya: *Umumta'lim maktablarning boshlang'ich sinf maktab yoshdagi bolalar o'zlarining xoish-istaklarini imkoniyatlarini ob'yektiv baholashga qodir emasliklari ularning asosiy qiziqish sabablarini o'rganish o'quvchilari orasidan iqtidorlilarini saralab olish (seleksiya) va ularni maqsadli tayyorlash vazifalari muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Umumta'lim maktab, qobiliyat, sport iqtidori, sport turlari.*

The problems of selecting talented children for sports requires improvement and continuous research. The scientific basis of the methods of selecting children for sports schools, forecasting future results, starting from children's sports to high-performance sports is considered an important and indispensable step.

Children's satisfaction with the initial results in sports is directly proportional to the correct choice of the sport. Therefore, choosing the right sport is a process controlled by teachers, sports coaches, and the general public, not by trying again and again. Children's selection and sports orientation are carried out through the "sportogram" (requirements, talents and abilities of a particular type of sport for the body).

Ability is a conditional need in relation to the specified activity, efficiency as a result of quick acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the tasks related to the activity.

Sports talent is a combination of activity-oriented abilities to achieve efficiency by easily performing physical movements according to the anatomo-physiological characteristics of the body.

Sports orientation is a system of activities aimed at a person's participation in a certain type of sport, forecasting his interest and satisfaction with future sports activities.

The task of developing the popularity of physical education and sports is related to the regular involvement of as many children as possible in this activity. Based on the opinions of a number of authors, among the tasks of the primary sports training stage of children's and teenagers' sports schools, it is important to determine the issues aimed at strengthening the health of students, increasing the level of physical development, and educating moral duty and voluntary qualities. is enough.

In most sports schools, it was found that 10-20% of students were not satisfied with the primary sports preparation groups. Some mistakes in the organization of the training process and general slowness of educational and promotional work were observed as the reasons for low efficiency.

According to sports coaches, it was recognized that most of the students who stopped their sports activities for some reasons can achieve high results in their first sports specialty. The reason for irrational departures from the spot should be found in the tools and methods used in the educational process and educational work. In addition, the reason for leaving sports schools early is the lack of professional skills of coaches and students. According to the results of a survey conducted among students (n = 20) who participated for a certain period of time in the group of children's sports preparation (for example, wrestling) of sports schools, 100% unanimous desire to engage in sports , along with positive attitudes towards teamwork in the group and attention from the coach, lack of desire to participate in competitions as the main reason was 25% (ages 9-10).

It was also found that children of primary (1-4th grade) school age in comprehensive schools are not able to objectively assess the possibilities of their wishes, that is, their main reason for interest is to become a champion (n=78%) is enough. In addition, among the main directions of the development program is the selection of talented athletes from among the students of educational institutions, aimed at evaluating some elements of team work, competition, debates, that is, at the early stages of student sports education. (selection) and the tasks of their targeted training are important.

Parents' relations are also considered an important factor in ensuring the effectiveness of the tasks of choosing the primary sports specialty by the students,

gradually strengthening skills in sports training. Parents of students who have observed negative interruptions at the stage of primary sports training, do not have systematic information about the impact and importance of sports on personal development, body and daily life. One of the most unpleasant situations is when we consider family life duties more important than the prospects of our children.

In educational institutions and among the general public, promotion activities are the basis of activities aimed at popularizing special knowledge about sports activities and forming children's interests. In practice, it is mainly carried out by providing short theoretical knowledge in the course of physical education lessons, working outside the classroom, in competitions (individual advice and instructions). As a result of pedagogic observations, due to the unsystematic continuity of the important process and the inefficiency in the use of the most basic non-scientific forms and methods, they could not explain the interest and aspirations of most elementary school students. That is, according to the results of the survey, only 22% of 77 elementary school students independently explain their attitude to sports.

1. The technological approach of the following order is recommended for qualifying children for sports in the course of physical education from the first grade of general education schools.
2. 1. Individual determination of abilities of 1st-4th grade students in a set of tests specific to various types of sports operating in general education schools, residences, and neighborhoods.
3. 2. Provide parents with detailed information about nearby sports clubs.
4. 3. Introducing students to Olympic sports in the content of physical education.
5. 4. To study the characteristics of the development of physical qualities characteristic of the sensitive period, which are manifested in the natural dynamics of physical abilities in the characteristics of 6-10 years old.
6. 5. Mastering the technical elements of movements specific to sports by means of action games.
7. 6. To determine the natural talents of coordination abilities, individual inclination towards physical movement activity.
8. 7. Organizing various sports competitions among students and analyzing their results at the school level.
9. 8. Based on the mental characteristics of each student, to start involving them in sports games.

During the pedagogical observations, the prospects (motivation) of elementary school students for playing sports were studied (attitudes towards sports). The received answers can be divided into two groups according to their nature:

1. It is directly related to the motivation of sports activities.
- a feeling of satisfaction from beautiful, aesthetic actions;

- ability to manage oneself in changing situations;
- to gain the attention of others by being able to show the possibility;
- imitation of famous athletes.

2. Indirectly related to the motivation of sports activities.

- to be beautiful, strong and healthy;
- according to parents' wishes.

According to A.TS.Puni, elementary school students are characterized by the dynamism (variability) of motivation. According to statistical data, if the student decides to do sports based on his personal wishes and needs, it is observed that the rate of growth of the results is positive and there are relatively few cases of absenteeism [5].

The conclusion is that the issue of a systematic approach to solving the tasks of forming the student's desires and interests among the requirements of the DTS in the content of physical culture education is essentially a necessary condition.

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